

Electrochemical reactions at sacrificial electrodes. Part-XXI[†] : Synthesis of unique antimony(III) alkoxides

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Abstract : Electrochemical reactions of acetylacetone, cyanoacetamide, ethylcyanoacetate, ethylacetoacetate and diethylmalonate (RH₂) have been carried out in acetonitrile at sacrificial antimony anode using tetrabutylammonium chloride as supporting electrolyte. The products isolated from the anode compartment have been identified by elemental analysis and infrared spectral studies and are found to be unique antimony(III) alkoxides. Coordination compounds of all these products with 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl have also been synthesized electrochemically and characterized by various physical methods. All these reactions proceed with high current efficiencies.

Keywords : Antimony(III) alkoxide, electrochemical reactions, electrodes, synthesis.

Introduction

Electrochemical technique represents a green route in synthetic inorganic and organic chemistry and the technique is associated with several other advantages¹. In view of the fact that metal chelates, in general^{2,3} and antimony compounds in particular^{4,5} have several applications in industry and laboratory. It was considered worthwhile to explore the use of the green electrochemical technique for the synthesis of unique antimony(III) alkoxides and their coordination compounds.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of antimony(III) alkoxides :

Products of these electrochemical reactions are insoluble in commonly used organic solvents like chloroform, benzene, methanol, acetone, dimethyl sulphoxide, *N,N*-dimethyl formamide etc. All the products do not melt up to 300 °C, however, colour of these products changes at about 220 °C thereby indicating that these products decompose around this temperature. The analytical data (antimony, carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents in all the products) conform to the molecular formula Sb(RH)₃.

Infrared spectral data reveal that the characteristic absorption bands in all these products appear in the regions of 565–547 and 1160–1000 cm⁻¹. In case of the products of cyanoacetamide and ethylcyanoacetate, ab-

sorption bands are also observed in the regions of 2178–2173 and 510–480 cm⁻¹ in addition to the bands in the above regions.

The ν(Sb–O) bands are reported^{6,8} to appear in the region of 612–540 cm⁻¹ in metal alkoxides. The bands observed in the region of 565–547 cm⁻¹ in the present studies can thus be assigned to ν(Sb–O) modes.

Two bands (a strong band in the region of 1060–1000 cm⁻¹ and a weak band in the region of 1148–1060 cm⁻¹) are observed in the infrared spectrum of the products. These bands can be assigned to ν(C–O)M stretching vibrations^{7–15}. Appearance of stronger bands in the lower region indicates the polymeric structure of these products through alkoxy bridging. Insoluble behaviour of the products in various organic solvents and high melting point also support the polymeric nature of these compounds.

The bands at 2173 and 2178 cm⁻¹ in the electrochemical products of cyanoacetamide and ethylcyanoacetate can be assigned to ν(C≡N) vibrations¹⁶. Appearance of these bands in comparatively lower region indicates the formation of these products via structure (II) and (III). The other additional band in these products in the region of 510–480 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to ν(Sb–N) vibrations¹⁷.

Current efficiencies of these systems have also been determined and are quite high (0.75 to 0.95 g equivalent

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per Faraday) thereby indicating that the reactions leading to the formation of the products are the predominant reactions of these systems.

The reaction scheme can be written as :

The organic compounds (RH₂) yield the carbanion on reduction at inert cathode :

These carbanions are stabilized through resonance :

R and R' represent methyl or ethoxy group

These anions react at sacrificial antimony anode to yield unique antimony(III) alkoxides :

Coordination compounds of the unique antimony(III) alkoxide :

Electrochemical products of the reactions of acetylacetone, cyanoacetamide, ethylcyanoacetate, ethylacetoacetate and diethylmalonate have been refluxed with ligands 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl separately in methanol, ethanol, benzene and acetonitrile for 48 h in order to prepare their coordination compounds. Analytical and infrared spectral data of these products show that the ligand molecules could not be attached to antimony(III) alkoxides to form their coordination compounds. It may be due to the reason that the metal in these alkoxides has already achieved its favourable coordination number through bridged alkoxy groups, therefore, further expansion of coordination sphere due to addition of ligand could not be achieved. It was thus considered worthwhile that the ligand may be added to these products electrochemically before these get polymerized.

The products so obtained are insoluble in commonly used organic solvents. The products do not melt up to 300 °C rather these decompose around 220 °C as indicated by their colour change. The analytical data conform to the molecular formula Sb(RH)₃.L.

Infrared spectral data recorded in potassium bromide pellets in the region of 4000–450 cm⁻¹ reveal that the characteristic absorption bands in all these products ap-

pear in the regions of 575–568, 1161–1020, 1463–1401 and 1625–1579 cm⁻¹.

A close study of the infrared data and the comparison of the data with that of the parent alkoxides reveals that the bands due to ν(Sb–O)⁶⁻⁸ and ν(C–O)Sb⁷⁻¹⁵ appearing in the regions of 575–568 and 1161–1020 cm⁻¹ respectively have shifted to the higher region.

The additional bands appearing in the region of 1625–1579 and 1463–1401 cm⁻¹ in these products may be due to ν(C–C) and ν(C–N) corresponding of the ligand molecules. However, these bands appear in slightly lower region than those reported for the pure ligand molecules¹⁸.

In case of electrochemical products of cyanoacetamide and ethylcyanoacetate band at 2168 cm⁻¹ in each product due to ν(C=N) and bands in the region of 524–490 cm⁻¹ due to ν(Sb–N)¹⁷ are also observed in addition to the above absorption bands. These bands, however, appear in higher region as compared to the parent products.

Appearance of the infrared bands due to the ligand molecules and shift of various bands as compared to the parent antimony(III) alkoxides confirm the coordination of the ligand molecules with the parent products. High melting point, insoluble behaviour and the infrared data indicates that these coordination products are also polymeric in nature like the parent chelates.

Current efficiencies of all these reactions have also been determined and are quite high (0.76 to 0.95 g equivalent per Faraday) thereby showing that the reactions leading to the formation of coordination compounds of antimony(III) alkoxides are the predominant reactions of these systems.

The present electrochemical technique thus presents a direct and single pot route for the synthesis of unique antimony(III) alkoxides and their coordination compounds.

Experimental

Acetonitrile was kept over phosphorus pentoxide for 24 h and then double distilled. Freshly distilled acetonitrile was used as solvent in all these reactions. Tetrabutylammonium chloride was crystallized from conductivity water and dried under reduced pressure at 100 °C. Electrolysis of the solution of 2.0 g of organic compound (RH₂) in acetonitrile (250 mL) containing tetrabutylammonium chloride (1.0 g) was carried out in H-type cell^{7,8}. Antimony sheet (2 × 10 × 0.2 cm³) was dipped in anode compartment and platinum foil (1.0 × 1.0 cm²)

in cathode compartment. Outlets were sealed after fitting the guard tubes. Necessary connections were made with Toshniwal electrophoresis power supply and potential across the electrodes was then adjusted so that a current of 20 mA passed through the solution. The electrolytic solution was stirred efficiently using magnetic stirrer.

Electrolysis was conducted for 10 h at a constant current of 20 mA. Solid products separated in anode compartment were filtered in filtration unit and washed with hot acetonitrile and dry ether and then dried under vacuum. All efforts were done to protect the products from air and moisture.

In order to synthesise the coordination compounds of the products of the above reactions, 1.0 g of the ligand (1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl) was also added to the reaction mixture before starting the electrolysis. The other details are the same as discussed above.

Melting point of all these products were determined using electrical device with a heating rate of 5 °C per minute.

Antimony contents in these products were determined iodometrically as discussed earlier^{7,8}. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen (where applicable) contents in the products were determined through microanalysis using Perkin-Elmer Elemental Analyser 2400 CHN.

Infrared spectra of the products have been recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (RXI) in the region of 4000–450 cm⁻¹ using potassium bromide pellets.

The current efficiencies (gram equivalents of metal dissolved per Faraday of electricity passed) of all these reactions were determined by electrolysis of the above systems for exactly two hours at a constant current of 20 mA as reported earlier^{7,8}.

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